

NARRATIVE OF RESISTANCE, MEMORY AND CULTURAL CONTINUITY IN THE CONTEXT OF WAR: A SYSTEMS APPROACH

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Abstracts. The study of commemorative practices in the context of contemporary conflicts, particularly the war in Ukraine, highlights the importance of visual images in shaping national identity and collective memory. Visual, symbolic, and documentary representations not only preserve historical heritage but also have a profound psychological impact, mobilizing society, fostering unity and patriotism, and supporting moral resilience. Special attention is given to the role of heroic images, symbols, monuments, and memorials, as well as depictions of war victims, civilian suffering, and cultural heritage, which preserve national identity and cultural memory in difficult times.

Keywords: commemoration, national identity, collective memory, visual images, Ukraine war.

Problem statement. Commemoration of war events has always been an integral part of the formation of national identity and collective memory. In the context of contemporary conflicts, images of war perform a dual task: providing a link to the past and constructing narratives that mobilise society to fight. Visual, symbolic, and documentary forms of depicting war not only preserve the historical heritage, but also affect the emotional state of citizens, their ability to unite and resist.

Overview of the current state of the art. This paper will provide an overview of the literature and various scholarly perspectives on decolonisation, national identity and memory in the context of contemporary conflicts, including the Russian aggression against Ukraine, which are highlighted by interdisciplinary approaches that shed light on the complex geopolitical, historical and cultural dynamics at play in this area. Barkawi (2022) analyzes the war in Ukraine through the lens of decolonization, emphasizing its historical and geopolitical significance. His work

examines how these processes reshape notions of sovereignty in contemporary conflicts. Blum (2007) investigates the formation of national identity among youth in the context of globalization in post-Soviet societies. The study underscores the challenges young people face in building a state identity while integrating into a globalized world. Eppinger (2022) discusses the transition from "limited sovereignty" to decolonization in Ukraine, exploring how the Soviet legacy manifests in contemporary identity politics. Mälksoo (2022) focuses on the postcolonial dimension of the Russia-Ukraine war, offering a framework that interprets the conflict as a rejection of imperial legacies. The research provides insights into how the postcolonial lens deepens our understanding of the causes and implications of the war. Marks (2000) examines cultural aspects of memory through cinema, delving into intercultural perspectives on war and collective remembrance. Her work enriches understanding by addressing how sensory and intercultural elements influence memory construction. Olivier (2019) analyzes issues of decolonization, identity, and neo-colonialism, exploring the relationships between colonial legacies and modern power structures. This study aids in comprehending neo-colonial challenges faced by independent nations. Tilmans, van Vree, and Winter (2010) investigate the intersection of memory, history, and identity in Europe. Their work offers a cultural perspective on how narratives influencing collective consciousness are formed. Vorbrugg and Jevgeniy (2022) concentrate on the political geography of knowledge and expertise, analyzing how the Western world attempts to contextualize the Russia-Ukraine war within the broader scope of global conflicts. Young (1994) explores Holocaust memorials as symbols of collective memory, providing parallels for understanding how similar approaches could be applied to preserving the memory of other tragedies.

Main text. The study of commemorative practices is an urgent task for the humanities, as they reveal the dynamics of social perceptions, emotional reactions and behavioural patterns during conflicts. The diversity of heroic, commemorative, cultural and symbolic images creates a unique space for studying the mechanisms of influence on the collective consciousness. Particularly important are aspects of their psychological impact, including motivation to act, maintaining collective cohesion, and preserving cultural identity.

The analysis of the key categories of commemoration in images and their place in contemporary Ukrainian society focuses on the multifaceted forms of their influence - from mobilisation and patriotism to the experience of grief and loss. The systematic approach to understanding these images allows us to understand how the narrative of resistance, memory and cultural continuity is created in the context of war.

Heroic images and symbols of courage are key to maintaining national identity, fostering patriotic feelings and building resilience in a society in times of war. They encompass a wide range of visual and narrative elements, including images of contemporary warriors, historical figures, important events in national history, and symbols of military victory. Images of heroic warriors personify strength, courage

and indomitability, which helps society feel confident in its ability to defend its land. These images build trust in the strength of the nation and inspire pride in the heroes of today who selflessly fulfil their duty to the state. Historical figures, symbols of prominent national heroes, are also of great importance, as they establish a link between generations, inspire new feats and remind us of the centuries-long struggle for independence. Significant past events emphasise the continuity of the struggle, and national symbols such as flags, coats of arms, emblems support a sense of unity and identity, uniting the people in a common narrative of resilience.

Sacrifice and remembrance of the dead is another important category of commemorations that focuses on honouring the memory of those who gave their lives for freedom. Memorial candles symbolise grief, eternal rest of souls and honour their feat, reminding us of the importance of preserving this memory. Monuments and military cemeteries serve as materialised manifestations of shared grief and collective memory, and at the same time become places of emotional unity. The images of fallen heroes, through their realistic portraits, create a strong emotional connection between those who are left alive and those who gave their lives, evoking gratitude, deep respect and a desire to continue their work with dignity.

Visual narratives of civilian suffering focus on the destruction, pain and loss experienced by ordinary people. These images become a mirror of the tragedy of war and the difficult circumstances faced by civilians. Their impact is multifaceted: on the one hand, they evoke empathy and compassion, motivating people to actively help the victims; on the other hand, they contribute to the realisation of the cost of peace by demonstrating the real scale of grief. The images of destroyed buildings, injured people and devastated territories convince us of the need to act to restore normal life and avoid the recurrence of such tragedies in the future.

National and cultural symbols are particularly important in preserving the identity of the people in times of war. Landscapes of the native land, picturesque architectural elements, ethnographic motifs, national clothes and symbols such as the trident or viburnum affirm the beauty and uniqueness of the nation's heritage. They awaken a sense of love for the native land and emphasise the importance of preserving and honouring national traditions. A special place is occupied by traditional ornaments, which serve as a reminder of the nation's roots, preserve cultural memory and inspire a sense of unity in difficult times.

The images of unity and solidarity demonstrate the collective strength of the people, their unity around common goals and mutual support. Group photographs that capture moments of unity, such as during volunteer activities or public events, evoke a sense of belonging and security. Allegories of the struggle for freedom, such as hands with a shield, birds or other symbolic images, add strength and optimism. Flags of friendly countries and references to international assistance symbolise solidarity with the global community and give confidence in the rightness of the chosen path.

Images of resistance and struggle against the aggressor represent a negative character, the enemy, in a satirical or allegorical form. Cartoons reduce fear, help to

realise moral superiority and demonstrate the resilience of the people. Scenes of victory, inspired by successes on the battlefield or in diplomatic confrontation, call for faith in one's own strength and justice. Symbolic allegories, such as a hand with a sword, remind us once again of the indomitable spirit of the people.

Real evidence of war becomes the strongest argument against aggression. Photographs, documentary videos, art posters, and modern interactive digital projects not only record tragic events, but also become a way to convey them to future generations. They allow us to experience events with emotional immersion, creating new means of memorialising historical moments.

Table 1 : systematic approach to understanding these images allows us to understand how the narrative of resistance, memory and cultural continuity is created in the context of war

Category	Image type	Description	Psychological aspect
Heroic images and symbols of courage	Images of warriors and defenders	Images of modern military heroes who personify the strength, courage and resilience of the nation.	They inspire pride, trust, and confidence in the people's ability to resist the aggressor.
	Historical figures	Images of prominent national heroes of the past that symbolise the continuity of the struggle and national dignity.	They keep generations connected, inspire heroic deeds, and awaken patriotic consciousness.
	Historical events	Depictions of key events in national history that point to the traditions of the struggle for independence.	They strengthen the sense of national pride and identity, create a common narrative about the heroism of the people.
	Symbols of military victory	Flags, coats of arms, emblems of military formations that remind of strength and patriotism.	They build unity, patriotism, and resilience in the fight for national interests.
Sacrifice and memory of the dead	Memorial candles	The image of candles as a symbol of grief and commemoration of the dead.	They evoke sadness and remind us of the importance of honouring those who gave their lives.
	Monuments	Memorials dedicated to the dead, symbolising the sacrifice and tragedy of war.	They reinforce the memory of the dead, evoke an emotional response and a sense of loss.
	Cemeteries	Depiction of military cemeteries as symbolic places of memory of the fallen.	They evoke sadness and remind us of the sacrifices made in the struggle for freedom.
	Visual narratives of civilian suffering	Images of destruction and injuries illustrating the suffering of civilians.	They evoke empathy and motivation to help victims and support their recovery.
	Portraits of fallen heroes	Realistic portraits of fallen defenders that become part of the collective memory.	They create an emotional connection, inspire gratitude and respect.
National and cultural symbols	Images of the native land	Landscapes and architectural landscapes that emphasise the importance of the national territory and its beauty.	They evoke love for the native land and form a sense of connection with the cultural heritage.
	Ornaments and ethnographic motifs	The use of ornaments that reflect folk motifs and traditional elements that reinforce cultural identity.	They support national identity and promote cultural awareness.
	National clothes	Depicting traditional costumes as visual symbols of national identity.	They evoke pride in cultural heritage and strengthen national identity.

Category	Image type	Description	Psychological aspect
	Traditional symbols (trident, viburnum, willow)	Emblems that reinforce national pride and emphasise the cultural connection to Ukrainian heritage.	They build pride in their country, strengthen identity and community.
Images of unity and solidarity	Group images	People uniting in support, symbolising cohesion around a common goal.	They evoke a sense of support and protection, and promote collective unity.
	Allegories of the struggle for freedom	The images of birds, hands with a sword or shield symbolise the will to freedom and steadfastness in the struggle.	They support the patriotic spirit and give confidence in the fight for freedom.
	International support	Flags of other countries or symbols of solidarity that express support for international allies.	They evoke a sense of global support and confidence in the rightness of their struggle.
Images of resistance and struggle against the aggressor	Caricatures of the enemy	Depictions of the aggressor in a satirical form that demonstrate a negative attitude towards him.	They reduce fear and form a critical attitude towards the aggressor.
	Scenes of victory and confrontation	Moments of physical and spiritual victory that emphasise the people's ability to resist the aggressor.	It strengthens the fortitude and belief in victory.
	Allegories of struggle (hand with a sword, crown of thorns)	Symbols that emphasise the indomitable spirit and strength of resistance.	They support the spirit of resistance, give confidence in the duration of the struggle and possible victory.
Real footage from the war and documentary evidence	Photos of the fighting	Real images from the battlefield documenting the chronicle of the war.	They evoke an emotional response and support the memory of events.
	Documentary videos	Video archives of events that capture real moments and provide true information about the war.	They maintain awareness and create a reliable picture of events.
	Art posters	Artistic images that become part of the visual archive of the war form images of heroism and patriotism.	They form a lasting memory of the war, inspire pride and respect for the heroes.
	Digital memorial projects	Interactive projects (VR, AR) that allow you to preserve your memory and relive events in a new format.	They allow for a deeper understanding and emotional experience of historical events, and preserve them in digital culture.

All these images together have a multifaceted psychological impact. They create a sense of involvement in a common cause, pride in the country and its heritage, and motivate resilience and struggle. At the same time, they help to survive the pain of loss and focus attention on the values of peace, freedom and compassion. All these visual elements become key to maintaining national identity, moral resilience and collective memory in times of war.

Conclusions. The commemoration of war events through images plays a critical role in shaping national identity and collective memory, particularly during times of conflict such as the ongoing war in Ukraine. Visual representations not only preserve historical heritage but also have a profound psychological impact on citizens, serving to unite, motivate, and galvanize society in the face of adversity. Heroic symbols, monuments, and memorials reinforce the continuity of the nation's struggle and resilience, fostering a sense of unity and pride. Images of sacrifice, civilian suffering,

and cultural symbols serve as powerful reminders of the cost of war, deepening the emotional connection between generations and affirming the importance of collective action to secure a peaceful future.

The multi-dimensional nature of these visual narratives reveals the complex mechanisms by which memory, identity, and patriotism are constructed and preserved, demonstrating the integral role of commemorative practices in times of war. Ultimately, these images shape not only the present narrative but also ensure that the memories of sacrifice and unity will persist for future generations, strengthening the cultural and historical foundations of society.

Funding. The work is performed within the research CEFRES, UAR 3138 CNRS–MEAE Research topic «Visual Narratives, Commemoration of War and Graphic Representation of National Identity: Comparative Analysis of Ukrainian and European Contexts».

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